

Joint Accuracy and Latency Optimization for Quantized Federated Learning in Vehicular Networks

Xinran Zhang¹, Graduate Student Member, IEEE, Weilong Chen, Hui Zhao, Graduate Student Member, IEEE, Zheng Chang², Senior Member, IEEE, and Zhu Han³, Fellow, IEEE

Abstract—Nowadays, the vehicular networks have emerged as a boosting technology to enhance traffic efficiency and safety within the transportation systems. As the amount of onboard data increases and the data privacy concerns grow, federated learning (FL) has gained popularity for harnessing the data for intelligent transportation operations. To satisfy the strict latency criteria in the vehicular networks, a quantization scheme is employed within FL to reduce the size of the local models before uplink transmission. In this article, considering the nature of vehicles' high mobility, we aim to optimize both the learning performance and latency simultaneously by jointly considering the communication resource budget and quantization strategies. Specifically, we first analyse the convergence performance of the quantized FL, which demonstrates the effects of both the quantization error and the number of clients on the convergence rate. Then, we formulate a multiobjective optimization problem (MOP) to maximize the number of participating clients and minimize the overall latency, by jointly optimizing the quantization level, wireless resource allocation, and client selection. To deal with the MOP, we decompose the MOP into a set of scalar optimization subproblems, each formulated as a Markov decision process (MDP). To solve the MDP in high-mobile vehicular networks, we propose a novel deep reinforcement learning-based vehicle heterogeneous quantization FL (DRL-VQFL) method, which leverages a DRL framework built upon the proximal policy optimization algorithm. Then, a parameter transfer strategy is employed to solve the neighboring subproblems efficiently. Our extensive simulations demonstrate the effectiveness and efficiency of the DRL-VQFL approach, showcasing its superiority over the other benchmark methods.

Index Terms—Client selection, communication efficiency, deep reinforcement learning, federated learning (FL), multiobjective optimization, quantization, vehicular network, wireless resource allocation.

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Xinran Zhang, Weilong Chen, Hui Zhao and Zheng Chang are with the School of Computer Science and Engineering, University of Electronic Science and Technology of China, Chengdu 611731, China (e-mail: zhangxinran@std.uestc.edu.cn; chenweilong1995@std.uestc.edu.cn; 202211081354@std.uestc.edu.cn; zheng.chang@jyu.fi).

Zhu Han is with the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Houston, Houston, TX 77004 USA, and also with the Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Kyung Hee University, Seoul 446-701, South Korea (e-mail: hanzhu22@gmail.com).

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I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background

VEHICULAR networks play a pivotal role in supporting the evolution of the intelligent transportation systems (ITSs) [1], enabling seamless wireless connections among vehicles, roadside units (RSUs), and pedestrians [2]. Equipped with vast amounts of sensors, vehicles generate ever-increasing onboard data that can be delivered through these vehicular networks [3]. To pave the way for information exchange, vehicle-to-vehicle and vehicles-to-infrastructure communication have emerged as two primary communication types in the vehicular networks [4].

With the remarkable growth in the vehicular data and the expansion of vehicular computing and storage capabilities, machine learning (ML) has been widely employed to create safer and more convenient driving conditions [5]. By leveraging the wealth of the collected data, ML provides intelligent predictions and adaptive decision making to facilitate an ocean of applications, including adaptive resource allocation policies, smart traffic operations, rapid attack identification, autonomous driving, and so on [6].

To learn a shared ML model, large amounts of data are transmitted from the local vehicles to the central server, which raises the data privacy concerns and fails to meet the stringent communication delay requirement in the vehicular networks. Nowadays, federated learning (FL) [7] has been regarded as a promising approach to tackle these ongoing challenges. In FL, the clients learn their local models by leveraging the data stored on their respective devices and subsequently upload the models to the server. Once the server collects these local models, it aggregates them into an updated global model, which will then be broadcast to all the clients for the next round of training. By utilizing the distributed computing and storage facilities on the clients, FL can expedite the training process without compromising data privacy [8].

B. Related Work

1) *FL in Vehicular Networks*: Assisted by various techniques, vehicular networks play a crucial role in advancing autonomous vehicles, traffic management systems, and the development of smart cities. Raza et al. [9] introduced the potential of vehicular edge computing in supporting real-time vehicular interactions by enabling the computation close

to the vehicular data source. Moreover, Tang et al. [10] investigate the pivotal role of ML in enhancing vehicular networks, focusing on applications, such as radio resource allocation, transmit scheduling, communication power control, traffic offloading, and dynamic routing. To preserve the clients' privacy in a communication-efficient manner within the vehicular networks, FL is regarded as a promising technique by pushing the computation to vehicles and employing the ML models to analyse vast amounts of data [11].

During the deployment of FL in vehicular networks, several challenges emerge due to communication bottlenecks, system heterogeneity, and heterogeneous data. To tackle these problems, various techniques have been proposed, including client selection, resource allocation, and incentive design. Zhao et al. [12] maximized the number of vehicles while considering dynamic wireless channels and varying computation capacities, ensuring tasks are completed within specified latency constraints. An over-the-air computation (AirComp)-based method is proposed in [13] to improve communication efficiency in FL by leveraging wireless channel superposition. To further minimize the communication overhead in practical AirComp-based FL systems, a convergence analysis is conducted in [14] to reveal the impact of the aggregation error caused by the channel fading and noise. Zeng et al. [15] analysed how the mobility of vehicles and the nonindependent and identically distributed (non-iid) nature of data have an impact on the FL convergence, and propose a contract theory-based incentive mechanism to accelerate the FL convergence speed. To strive for the lowest cost in the worst-case scenario of FL, Xiao et al. [16] considered the vehicles' position and velocity, and present a vehicle selection and resource allocation optimization method to minimize the overall system cost.

2) *Quantization in FL*: Despite FL involving parameter exchanges instead of raw data, communication efficiency remains a bottleneck due to the increasing size and complexity of neural networks (NNs) as the FL tasks become more complex. The quantization scheme emerges as an effective solution to mitigate this issue, where the trained models are compressed before the uplink transmission [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22], [23]. The work in [17] highlights the profound impacts of the physical layer quantization and transmission options on the convergence of FL. To enhance energy efficiency and reduce the number of global rounds, [18] introduces a multiobjective optimization problem (MOP) to optimize the quantization level. Moreover, how to minimize the service delay for FL by controlling the local updates, the weight quantization level and gradient quantization level is analysed in [19].

The devices in the FL systems often exhibit heterogeneity in communication and computing capabilities, but prior works overlook the system distinctions by assuming a homogeneous quantization scheme across all the devices. Following that, Chen et al. [24] proposed FEDHQ to assign different aggregation weights and set heterogeneous quantization levels for the devices. Considering the tradeoff between the quantization error and the transmission outage under restricted transmission delay, Wang et al. [25] presented FedTOE to enhance the

model accuracy through a theoretic convergence analysis. Moreover, to deal with the statistical heterogeneity and device heterogeneity, QuPeD [26] is a novel scheme to allow clients to learn the compressed and personalized models with varying quantization levels and model dimensions. The resources and the personalized quantization bits are jointly optimized in [27] to mitigate the communication bottleneck issue. Given that the client's location changes in FL can introduce variations in the wireless channels, Lan et al. [28] investigated the heterogeneous quantization when dealing with varying channels in the wireless FL. In the vehicular networks, the system heterogeneity is a prevalent feature, prompting the adoption of a heterogeneous quantization method in this article.

While various heterogeneous quantization schemes are investigated, the aforementioned studies primarily focus on the general wireless FL systems, overlooking the distinctive challenges posed by vehicular networks, including stringent real-time communication requirements and precise learning performance demands. Li et al. [29] implemented heterogeneous quantization precisions in vehicular networks. To improve communication efficiency and minimize aggregated squared quantization errors within vehicular ad hoc networks, FEDDO is proposed to assign different aggregation weights to the local models with individual quantization precisions. It is worth noting that the quantization scheme reduces the training latency at the expense of compromising the FL learning performance. Hence, it is pivotal to design an appropriate quantization strategy to balance the FL accuracy and training latency.

C. Motivation and Contributions

As a pivotal characteristic of vehicular networks, these existing works disregard the nature of vehicles' high mobility when applying the heterogeneous quantization scheme. Vehicles may move out of the coverage range of RSUs with high speeds, exacerbating the straggler effect. Furthermore, the nature of vehicles' mobility results in varying wireless conditions across different FL global rounds, further impacting the system communication efficiency. Given the constraints of limited wireless resources in vehicular networks, it is critical to jointly optimize wireless resource allocation and quantization levels that can adapt to the dynamic mobility of vehicles.

Motivated by the aforementioned observations, this article studies the performance of FL under the quantization scheme and aims to deal with these difficulties in vehicular networks. Specifically, we first provide a convergence rate analysis for FL while considering the heterogeneous quantization schemes. Then, to improve the FL accuracy and reduce the latency, we formulate an MOP and aim to optimize the bandwidth allocation, client selection, and quantization levels. To solve the mixed integer nonlinear programming problem, we employ deep reinforcement learning-based vehicle heterogeneous quantization FL (DRL-VQFL) to obtain the optimal solutions efficiently. In particular, the main contributions of our work include as follows.

- 1) We investigate FL implementation in vehicular networks characterized by highly mobile vehicles. To alleviate the

straggler effect arising from the mobility of vehicles, we propose a vehicle selection mechanism. Then, to effectively account for the dynamic wireless environment incurred by the vehicles' high mobility, we model the FL process as a Markov decision process (MDP), and derive the dynamic wireless channel conditions required for calculating the total latency.

- 2) We leverage the heterogeneous quantization scheme to reduce the communication delay and conduct a convergence rate analysis to study how quantization errors and the number of participating users impact the performance of FL. To ensure FL accuracy, we aim to improve the number of participating vehicles while effectively managing the quantization error introduced by the quantization method. Following that, we formulate an MOP to maximize the number of participating participants and minimize the overall latency. To accomplish this, we explore the tradeoff between these two objectives by jointly optimizing quantization levels, bandwidth allocation, and vehicle selection indices.
- 3) To obtain the feasible solution to the MOP problem, we propose the DRL-VQFL algorithm. We break down the MOP into multiple subproblems, subsequently modeling each of these subproblems using an NN. In addressing these subproblems, we treat each as an MDP and apply a proximal policy optimization (PPO)-based approach to find solutions effectively.
- 4) Finally, to validate the effectiveness of our proposed scheme, we evaluate the performance of DRL-VQFL through the comprehensive simulations utilizing the open data sets and models. The simulation results demonstrate the superiority of our proposed method over other baselines, particularly in terms of communication efficiency and model accuracy.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. In Section II, we introduce the system model of quantized FL in the vehicular networks. The convergence rate of the heterogeneous quantization FL and vehicles' mobility are investigated in Section III. Section IV formulates the optimization problem. In Section V, the DRL-VQFL algorithm is developed to solve the formulated MOP. Simulation results are presented in Section VI. Finally, Section VII concludes this article.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In this section, we first present the FL workflow in the vehicular network. Then, we introduce a quantization scheme to reduce communication delays. Next, we elaborate on the latency costs. As depicted in Fig. 1, we consider an urban road where there is one RSU and a set $\mathcal{K} = \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ of vehicles collaboratively learning the FL model.

A. FL Model

We define the set of the global communication rounds as $\mathcal{M} = \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$. Given the constraints of limited wireless resources and the dynamic mobility of vehicles, only a subset $\mathcal{N}_m \in \mathcal{K}$ of vehicles can participate in the FL task, with $|\mathcal{N}_m| = N$. With a variety of onboard sensors, each vehicle

Fig. 1. Workflow of the quantized FL in vehicular networks.

$k \in \mathcal{N}_m$ first collects its private data set \mathcal{D}_k with the data size $D_k = |\mathcal{D}_k|$. In the supervised learning tasks, we have $\mathcal{D}_k = \{\mathcal{X}_k, \mathcal{Y}_k\}$, where $\mathcal{X}_k = \{x_{k,1}, x_{k,2}, \dots, x_{k,D_k}\}$ represents the training data and $\mathcal{Y}_k = \{y_{k,1}, y_{k,2}, \dots, y_{k,D_k}\}$ refers to the labels of the vehicle k . This data can be utilized for various FL tasks, and all the vehicles jointly train a global FL model guided by the RSU.

The primary objective of the FL task is to minimize the global loss function by identifying the optimal global model parameters \mathbf{w} : $\min_{\mathbf{w}} F(\mathbf{w}) = \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_m} \rho_k F_k(\mathbf{w})$, where $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{R}^J$ represents the J -dimensional global model parameters, $\rho_k = (D_k / \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_m} D_k)$ represents the weight of vehicle k , and we have $\sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_m} \rho_k = 1$.

Let $l(\mathbf{w}; x_{k,v}, y_{k,v})$ denote the loss function for each data sample $v \in \mathcal{D}_k$. Then, the local loss function generated by the vehicle k can be denoted as $F_k(\mathbf{w})$, which is expanded as

$$F_k(\mathbf{w}) \triangleq \frac{1}{D_k} \sum_{v \in \mathcal{D}_k} l(\mathbf{w}; x_{k,v}, y_{k,v}). \quad (1)$$

We define the local training rounds as $\mathcal{I} = \{1, 2, \dots, I\}$. Let \mathbf{w}_m denote the global model at global round m and $\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^i$ as the local model of vehicle k in local round i at global round m . Then, by employing the local stochastic gradient descent (SGD) method, the vehicle k updates its local model parameters at the global communication round m as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{w}_{k,m}^0 &= \mathbf{w}_{m-1} \\ \mathbf{w}_{k,m}^i &= \mathbf{w}_{k,m}^{i-1} - \eta_m \nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^{i-1}, \xi_{k,m}^{i-1}) \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{I} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where η_m corresponds to the lr at global round m . Additionally, $\xi_{k,m}^{i-1}$ represents a mini-batch, which is a sample uniformly selected from the local data set \mathcal{D}_k .

To reduce the data size for transmission, the vehicles can upload a weight differential $\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}$ as proposed by [25] and [27]

$$\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m} = \mathbf{w}_{k,m}^I - \mathbf{w}_{k,m}^0 = -\eta_m \sum_{i=1}^I \nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^{i-1}, \xi_{k,m}^{i-1}) \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^I$ is the calculated local model after I local rounds and serves as the updated result for aggregation in the RSU. We adopt $\mathbf{w}_{k,m}$ to represent $\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^I$ to simplify the notations for further analysis.

Then, by aggregating all the local weight differentials, we can obtain the global model parameters \mathbf{w}_m

$$\mathbf{w}_m = \mathbf{w}_{m-1} + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_m} \rho_k \Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}. \quad (4)$$

B. Quantization Scheme

To mitigate transmission latency, the quantization scheme is leveraged to compress the NN parameters into a smaller quantization level. Let $Q(\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m})$ represent the quantized weight differential of vehicle k at global round m for transmission, and (4) can be changed as

$$\mathbf{w}_m = \mathbf{w}_{m-1} + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_m} \rho_k Q(\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}). \quad (5)$$

We denote $\Delta w_{k,m}^{\max}$ and $\Delta w_{k,m}^{\min}$ as the upper and lower bounds of the absolute values of parameters $w_{k,m,j}$ ($j \in \{1, 2, \dots, J\}$) in the J -dimensional vector parameters $\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}$, such that $\Delta w_{k,m}^{\max} = \max\{|\Delta w_{k,m,j}|\}$ and $\Delta w_{k,m}^{\min} = \min\{|\Delta w_{k,m,j}|\}$. Then, we have $\Delta w_{k,m}^{\min} \leq |\Delta w_{k,m,j}| \leq \Delta w_{k,m}^{\max}$. We employ stochastic rounding [30] in the quantization method, denoting $q_{k,m}$ as the quantization bits for the vehicle k at global round m . Then, there are $2^{q_{k,m}}$ integer values, and $[\Delta w_{k,m}^{\min}, \Delta w_{k,m}^{\max}]$ can be divided into $2^{q_{k,m}} - 1$ intervals, denoted as $V_\varphi = [z_\varphi, z_{\varphi+1}]$, where $\varphi \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^{q_{k,m}} - 2\}$. The value of the knob z_φ is given by

$$z_\varphi = \Delta w_{k,m}^{\min} + \varphi \times \frac{\Delta w_{k,m}^{\max} - \Delta w_{k,m}^{\min}}{2^{q_{k,m}} - 1}$$

where $\varphi \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 2^{q_{k,m}} - 1\}$.

When the value of $\Delta w_{k,m}$ falls within the interval V_φ , the quantization function can be written as

$$Q(\Delta w_{k,m}) = \begin{cases} \text{sign}(\Delta w_{k,m,j}) \cdot z_\varphi, & \text{w.p. } \iota \\ \text{sign}(\Delta w_{k,m,j}) \cdot z_{\varphi+1}, & \text{w.p. } (1 - \iota) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where we have $\iota = (z_{\varphi+1} - |\Delta w_{k,m,j}|) / (z_{\varphi+1} - z_\varphi)$ and the sign function $\text{sign}(\cdot)$ yields the sign of $\Delta w_{k,m,j}$ as -1 or 1 . Moreover, ‘‘w.p.’’ is short for ‘‘with probability.’’

The size of the quantized weight differential $Q(\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m})$ can be calculated as

$$e_{k,m} = Jq_{k,m} + \alpha \quad (7)$$

where α is the sum of the number of bits to represent the sign, and the size of $\Delta w_{k,m}^{\max}$ and $\Delta w_{k,m}^{\min}$.

Utilizing the quantization function defined above, we can obtain the following lemma like [25] and [27].

Lemma 1: The quantized parameter $Q(\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m})$ remains unbiased with respect to $\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}$. Moreover, let $\beta_{k,m} = [J/4](\Delta w_{k,m}^{\max} - \Delta w_{k,m}^{\min})^2$ and the quantization error can be bounded as follows:

$$\mathbb{E}[Q(\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m})] = \Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}$$

$$\mathbb{E}[\|Q(\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}) - \Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}\|_2^2] \leq \frac{\beta_{k,m}}{(2^{q_{k,m}} - 1)^2} \triangleq O_{k,m}. \quad (8)$$

Proof: Both the equality can be obtained by calculating the expectation with the quantization method in (6). Further details of this derivation can be found in [25]. ■

Lemma 1 reveals that a smaller value of the quantization bit $q_{k,m}$ results in a higher quantization error, because a smaller $q_{k,m}$ leads to lower precision of the trained model.

C. Computation and Communication Model

1) *Local Computation:* Nowadays, vehicles can be equipped with GPU and possess abundant computational resources [31]. Unlike CPUs, which operate in a serial mode, GPUs function in parallel. When the training batch size (bs) is small, GPUs can process all the data simultaneously, resulting in a consistent computation latency. However, as the training bs surpasses the maximum number of data that can be processed at once, the latency increases. According to [32], the computation time $T_{k,m}^{\text{cp}}$ with bs ϕ can be defined as follows:

$$T_{k,m}^{\text{cp}} = \begin{cases} T_k^{\text{th}}, & \text{if } 1 \leq \phi_k \leq \phi_k^{\text{th}} \\ o_k(\phi_k - \phi_k^{\text{th}}) + T_k^{\text{th}}, & \text{if } \phi_k^{\text{th}} < \phi_k \leq \phi_k^{\text{max}} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

where T_k^{th}, o_k are the parameters related to the NN model and GPU configuration and ϕ_k^{th} is the threshold bs for the vehicle k .

2) *Uplink Communication:* We consider an orthogonal frequency domain multiple access (OFDMA) as the transmission scheme. The channel gain between the vehicle k and the RSU at global round m can be represented as follows [33]:

$$g_{k,m} = \frac{h_{k,m}}{(d_{k,m})^\nu} \quad (10)$$

where $h_{k,m}$ represents the power gain of the channel at a reference distance of 1 m, $d_{k,m}$ is the distance between the vehicle k and the RSU, and ν is the path loss exponent.

Let $p_{k,m}$ represent the uplink power. Then, the achievable uplink transmission rate is given by [34]

$$l_{k,m} = b_{k,m} B \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{p_{k,m} g_{k,m}}{\sigma^2} \right) \quad (11)$$

where B and σ^2 represent the total uplink bandwidth and the variance of the complex white Gaussian channel noise. Besides, the parameter $b_{k,m} \in (0, 1)$ denotes the allocated bandwidth index of vehicle k at global round m with $\sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_m} b_{k,m} = 1$.

Before uplink transmission, the model for the vehicle k at global round m is quantized with $q_{k,m}$ bits. Let e_o denote the original model size with q^{\max} bits. Since, α is much smaller than $Jq_{k,m}$, from (7) we can approximately calculate the size of the quantized data with $q_{k,m}$ bits as [18]

$$e_{k,m} = \frac{e_o q_{k,m}}{q^{\max}}. \quad (12)$$

Then, the uplink communication time $T_{k,m}^{\text{cm}}$ can be expressed as

$$T_{k,m}^{\text{cm}} = \frac{e_{k,m}}{l_{k,m}} = \frac{e_o q_{k,m}}{q^{\max} b_{k,m} B \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{p_{k,m} g_{k,m}}{\sigma^2} \right)}. \quad (13)$$

3) *Aggregation and Downlink Transmission*: Once having collected the local models, the RSU aggregates them into a global model and then broadcasts it to all the vehicles. The aggregation delay is typically negligible, as assumed in [35], due to its basic averaging operation, which can be rapidly performed using the RSU's high computational capacity.

Furthermore, the downlink delay is considered insignificant in comparison to the uplink delay, as presented in [36], due to the RSU's significantly higher downlink power and the allocation of a larger downlink bandwidth for data distribution.

4) *Total Latency*: Overall, the total latency at global round m can be calculated as the maximum latency among all the vehicles due to the straggler effect

$$T_m = \max_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \{T_{k,m}^{cp} + T_{k,m}^{cm}\}. \quad (14)$$

III. CONVERGENCE AND VEHICLES' MOBILITY ANALYSIS

In this section, we first derive the convergence of FL, followed by an analysis of the impacts on the performance of FL. Next, we model the dynamics of wireless networks caused by the vehicles' mobility and propose a vehicle selection mechanism.

A. Convergence Analysis

Before we discuss the convergence of FL, we consider the general assumptions of the loss function, which are similar to those in works [17], [18], and [37].

Assumption 1: $F_k(\mathbf{w})$ is L -smooth and lowered bounded for all $k \in \mathcal{K}$. For all \mathbf{w}_1 and \mathbf{w}_2 : $F_k(\mathbf{w}_2) - F_k(\mathbf{w}_1) \leq (\mathbf{w}_2 - \mathbf{w}_1)^T \nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_1) + (L/2)\|\mathbf{w}_2 - \mathbf{w}_1\|_2^2$, where $F_k(\mathbf{w}) \geq F \geq -\infty$.

Assumption 2: $F_k(\mathbf{w})$ is μ -strongly convex for all $k \in \mathcal{K}$. For all \mathbf{w}_1 and \mathbf{w}_2 : $F_k(\mathbf{w}_2) - F_k(\mathbf{w}_1) \geq (\mathbf{w}_2 - \mathbf{w}_1)^T \nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_1) + (\mu/2)\|\mathbf{w}_2 - \mathbf{w}_1\|_2^2$.

Assumption 3: For all $k \in \mathcal{K}$, the variance of stochastic gradients of the randomly sampled data $\xi_{k,m}$ for the vehicle k is bounded as $\mathbb{E}\|\nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^i, \xi_{k,m}^i) - \nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^i)\|_2^2 \leq \delta^2$, and SGD is unbiased: $\mathbb{E}\|\nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^i, \xi_{k,m}^i)\|_2 = \nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^i)$.

Assumption 4: For all $i \in \mathcal{I}, k \in \mathcal{K}$ and $m \in \mathcal{M}$, the expected second moment of the norm of stochastic gradients $\nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^i, \xi_{k,m}^i)$ is uniformly bounded as: $\mathbb{E}\|\nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^i, \xi_{k,m}^i)\|_2^2 \leq G^2$.

In addition, we use $\Gamma = F(\mathbf{w}^*) - \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_m} \rho_k F_k^*$ to quantify the degree of non-iid, where $F(\mathbf{w}^*)$ and F_k^* are the minimal values of F and F_k . Then, the upper bound of $\mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}(T))] - F(\mathbf{w}^*)$ is presented in Theorem 1 to display the convergence result as follows.

Theorem 1: Let Assumptions 1 to 4 hold. Let $\Delta_0 = \mathbb{E}\|\mathbf{w}_0 - \mathbf{w}^*\|_2^2$. If $\tau > \max\{2, (2/\mu), (L/\mu)\}$, and the lr $\eta_m = (2/\mu(\tau + m))$, $\mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}(M))] - F(\mathbf{w}^*)$ is bounded as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}_M)] - F(\mathbf{w}^*) &\leq \frac{L\tau}{2(\tau + M)} \Delta_0 + \frac{2L}{\mu^2(\tau + M)} \Phi_1 \\ &+ \underbrace{\Phi_2 \left(\frac{K}{N} - 1 \right)}_{\text{(a) caused by partial participants}} + \underbrace{\frac{L}{2} \left(\sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_m} \frac{\rho_k \beta_{k,m}}{(2^{q_{k,m}} - 1)^2} \right)}_{\text{(b) caused by quantization error}} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Fig. 2. Latency in one FL iteration considering vehicles' high mobility.

where $\Phi_1 = I^2 \delta^2 + 2LI^2 \Gamma + [IG^2(I-1)(2I-1)(\mu+2)/6] + IG^2$ and $\Phi_2 = [8LI^2 G^2 / \mu^2 (\tau + M)(K-1)]$.

Proof: Refer to the detailed proof the Appendix. ■

It can be observed that as the quantization bit $q_{k,m}$ increases, the upper bound of $\mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}_M)] - F(\mathbf{w}^*)$ decreases, resulting in improved convergence of FL. This observation aligns with the understanding that a smaller quantization bit may lead to more missing information, thus potentially reducing the model's accuracy. Furthermore, Theorem 1 also shows that an increase in the number of participants N can reduce the above upper bound, thereby enhancing the FL's performance, which is consistent with the conclusions drawn in [12] and [34].

B. Vehicles' Mobility and Selection Mechanism

1) *Vehicles' Mobility*: Due to the mobility of vehicles, the path loss in the uplink transmission varies and is determined by the distance between the RSU and the vehicle, as depicted in Fig. 2. We assume that the distance vehicle k has traveled at global round $m-1$ is denoted as $u_{k,m-1}$ and v is the velocity of vehicles. The traveling distance at global round m can be represented as

$$u_{k,m} = u_{k,m-1} + vT^{m-1}. \quad (16)$$

The traveling distance for the vehicles to upload the local parameters can be represented as $\hat{u}_{k,m} = u_{k,m-1} + T_{k,m}^{cp} v$. Let R represent the coverage radius of the RSU, and H denote the vertical distance between the RSU and the road. Then, the distance between the vehicle k and the RSU can be calculated as

$$d_{k,m} = \sqrt{\|R - \hat{u}_{k,m}\|^2 + H^2}. \quad (17)$$

2) *Vehicle Selection Mechanism*: The vehicles on the road are at varying speeds and the wireless conditions are highly dynamic. Therefore, the diverse remaining time for the vehicles in the RSU's coverage makes a great impact on the

FL training accuracy. Let $c_{k,m} \in \{0, 1\}$ represent the client selection index at global round m for the vehicle k . When the vehicle k is selected, $c_{k,m} = 1$. When the vehicle k is not selected, then $c_{k,m} = 0$. To ensure that selected vehicles can complete the task before leaving the RSU's coverage, we have

$$c_{k,m}u_{k,m} \leq 2R. \quad (18)$$

To avoid the straggler effect, we set a latency tolerance T^{\max} , represented as

$$T_m = \max_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\{ c_{k,m} \left(T_{k,m}^{cp} + T_{k,m}^{cm} \right) \right\} \leq T^{\max}. \quad (19)$$

IV. PROBLEM FORMULATION

In this section, we first discuss the two objectives for optimization and then formulate an MOP to simultaneously enhance the FL performance and reduce the total latency in the vehicular network.

Inspired by the conclusion after Theorem 1, we propose the following metric to measure the FL performance by calculating the number of participants, which can be expressed as follows:

$$G_m = \ln \left(1 + \sum_{k=1}^K c_{k,m} \rho_k \right) \quad (20)$$

where $c_{k,m}$ represents the selection index of the vehicle k at global round m . When more vehicles engage in the training, G_m becomes larger, indicating improved FL performance. It is noted that when no vehicles are selected, $\sum_{k=1}^K c_{k,m} = 0$, resulting in $G_m = 0$. Besides, as a concave increasing function, the logarithm function can better capture the relationship between the FL performance and the number of participants. This is because as the number of participating vehicles increases, the growth rate in the FL performance diminishes [38].

Next, we denote the vehicle selection indices, quantization levels, and bandwidth allocation for all the vehicles at global round m as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{C}_m &= [c_{1,m}, c_{2,m}, \dots, c_{K,m}] \\ \mathbf{Q}_m &= [q_{1,m}, q_{2,m}, \dots, q_{K,m}] \\ \mathbf{B}_m &= [b_{1,m}, b_{2,m}, \dots, b_{K,m}]. \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

To improve the FL performance, the problem of maximizing the accumulated number of participants can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\mathbf{C}} \sum_{m=1}^M f_1 &= \sum_{m=1}^M G_m \\ &= \sum_{m=1}^M \ln \left(1 + \sum_{k=1}^K c_{k,m} \rho_k \right) \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where $\mathbf{C} = [\mathbf{C}_1, \mathbf{C}_2, \dots, \mathbf{C}_M]$ is a metric of decision vectors \mathbf{C}_m for $m \in \mathcal{M}$.

In addition, the real-time feedback is critical in the vehicular networks for safety concerns, so another problem in minimizing the total latency can be described as

$$\min_{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{B}} \sum_{m=1}^M f_2 = \sum_{m=1}^M T_m$$

$$= \sum_{m=1}^M \max_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \left\{ c_{k,m} \left(T_{k,m}^{cp} + T_{k,m}^{cm} \right) \right\} \quad (23)$$

where $\mathbf{Q} = [\mathbf{Q}_1, \mathbf{Q}_2, \dots, \mathbf{Q}_M]$, and $\mathbf{B} = [\mathbf{B}_1, \mathbf{B}_2, \dots, \mathbf{B}_M]$ are the metrics of decision vectors \mathbf{Q}_m and \mathbf{B}_m for $m \in \mathcal{M}$.

Based on the above analysis, we formulate an MOP problem to maximize the weighted number of accumulated participants in FL and minimize the vehicles' total latency by jointly optimizing the selection indices \mathbf{C} , quantization level \mathbf{Q} , and bandwidth allocation \mathbf{B} . The problem can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{B}} f(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{B}) &= \left(\sum_{m=1}^M f_1(\mathbf{C}), - \sum_{m=1}^M f_2(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{B}) \right) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathcal{C}_1: \quad \sum_{m=1}^M \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{c_{k,m} \rho_k b_{k,m}}{(2^{q_{k,m}} - 1)^2} \leq \varepsilon \\ \mathcal{C}_2: \quad \sum_{k=1}^K c_{k,m} b_{k,m} = 1 \quad \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \\ \mathcal{C}_3: \quad q_{k,m} \in \mathbb{Z}_+ \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \\ \mathcal{C}_4: \quad 0 \leq b_{k,m} \leq 1 \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \\ \mathcal{C}_5: \quad c_{k,m} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \\ \mathcal{C}_6: \quad c_{k,m} u_{k,m} \leq 2R \quad \forall k \in \mathcal{K} \quad \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \\ \mathcal{C}_7: \quad T_m \leq T^{\max} \quad \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \\ \mathcal{C}_8: \quad \sum_{k=1}^K c_{k,m} \geq 1 \quad \forall m \in \mathcal{M} \end{array} \right. \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

where the constraint \mathcal{C}_1 limits an upper bound ε of the quantization error to ensure the FL performance based on the above convergence analysis. \mathcal{C}_2 ensures the sum of all allocated bandwidth equals 1. The constraints in \mathcal{C}_3 , \mathcal{C}_4 , and \mathcal{C}_5 limit the range of the three variables. In \mathcal{C}_6 , the selected vehicles are ensured to stay within the coverage area of the RSU. In \mathcal{C}_7 , the latency at one round must not exceed the latency tolerance to avoid the straggler effect. \mathcal{C}_8 guarantees at least one client participates to facilitate the FL training process.

Now, we have formulated an MOP problem involving vehicle selection, quantization levels assignment, and bandwidth allocation. Nevertheless, several challenges hinder deriving the optimal solution for the above problem. First, the three variable metrics are coupled with each other, with a mix of integer parameters and continuous variables, which complicates the optimization process. Second, the mobility of vehicles introduces uncertainty and high dynamics within vehicular networks. Third, the two objectives conflict with each other when dealing with the limited wireless resources within a predefined latency tolerance. To deal with these challenges, we propose the DRL-VQFL algorithm in the following section.

V. PROPOSED DRL-VQFL ALGORITHM

In this section, we propose DRL-VQFL to tackle the above MOP. First, we apply the decomposition strategy to divide the problem in (24) into several scalar optimization subproblems. Then, each subproblem is optimized in a sequence efficiently by the parameter transfer strategy [39], as displayed in Fig. 3.

A. DRL-VQFL Framework

To solve the MOP effectively, decomposition is regarded as the essential technique. In DRL-VQFL, we first apply the min-max scaling method adopted in [40] and [41] to normalize the objects with different scales, yielding \hat{f}_1 and \hat{f}_2 . Then, we

Fig. 3. Problem decomposition and parameter transfer process.

leverage the weighted sum method [42] to convert the bi-objective problem into the T scalar subproblems. We denote the set of weight vectors as $\lambda^1, \dots, \lambda^t, \dots, \lambda^T$, where $\lambda^t = (\lambda_1^t, \lambda_2^t)$, and $\lambda_1^t + \lambda_2^t = 1$. In our bi-objective problem, the set can be given as $(1, 0), (0.9, 0.1), \dots, (0, 1)$ [39]. Hence, the objective of the t th scalar optimization problem can be represented with the weight vector $\lambda^t = (\lambda_1^t, \lambda_2^t)$ as [43]

$$\max_{\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{B}} \lambda_1^t \bar{f}_1(\mathbf{C}) - \lambda_2^t \bar{f}_2(\mathbf{C}, \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{B}). \quad (25)$$

By applying different λ^t and solving all the T subproblems, we can obtain the Pareto optimal solutions, which together form the Pareto front (PF). It is noted that neighboring subproblems share adjacent weight vectors, which implies that they have similar solutions. Then, the solution to a subproblem can be obtained by transferring knowledge gained from its neighboring subproblems, as depicted in Fig. 3. Therefore, the neighborhood-based parameter transfer strategy [39] can be employed to transfer the model parameters from the previous subproblem to the current one, facilitating the collaborative and efficient resolution of all the scalar subproblems, as demonstrated in [44] and [45].

To deal with each subproblem, we model it as an NN and employ the DRL-based method to derive the optimal solutions. Specifically, we define the parameters of the network model of the t th subproblem as ω_{λ^t} with the optimal parameters $\omega_{\lambda^t}^*$. Then, $\omega_{\lambda^t}^*$ can be regarded as the initial parameters for training the network model in the $(t+1)$ th subproblem. Then, the decomposition and neighborhood-based parameter-transfer strategies allow for efficient training of the DRL-VQFL model, since all the subproblems can be solved in sequence by transferring the network weights. The general framework of DRL-VQFL is shown in Algorithm 1.

B. Markov Decision Process

To solve the decomposed scalar subproblems, each subproblem is modeled as an MDP $\langle \mathcal{S}, \mathcal{A}, \mathcal{P}, \mathcal{R} \rangle$, where \mathcal{S}

Algorithm 1: General Framework for DRL-VQFL to Solve MOP

- 1: **Input:** The subproblem model ω_{λ} and weight vectors $\lambda^1, \dots, \lambda^T$;
- 2: **Output:** The PF derived from all Pareto optimal solutions;
- 3: Randomly initialize the model parameters ω_{λ^1} .
- 4: **for** $t = 1$ **to** T **do**
- 5: **if** $t == 1$ **then**
- 6: Applying the PPO algorithm to learn the first subproblem model with the initial parameters ω_{λ^1} , the optimal model parameters $\omega_{\lambda^1}^*$ can be obtained.
- 7: **else**
- 8: $\omega_{\lambda^t} \leftarrow \omega_{\lambda^{t-1}}^*$.
- 9: Continuing to learn the subproblem t with the initial parameters ω_{λ^t} , the optimal model parameters $\omega_{\lambda^t}^*$ can be obtained.
- 10: **end if**
- 11: **end for**

is the state set, \mathcal{A} denotes the action set, \mathcal{P} represents the transition probabilities, and \mathcal{R} is the reward function. The RSU is regarded as the agent that observes the environmental information and conducts the calculations.

1) *State Space* \mathcal{S} : The state space is a collection of all observable environmental states within the system, capturing the dynamic changes occurring during each global round. At global round m , the state s_m includes the following elements:

$$s_m = \{\mathbf{u}_m, \mathbf{d}_m, \mathbf{g}_m, \mathbf{T}_m^{cm}, T_m\} \quad (26)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_m = [u_{1,m}, u_{2,m}, \dots, u_{k,m}]$ denotes the vehicles' traveling distances; $\mathbf{d}_m = [d_{1,m}, d_{2,m}, \dots, d_{k,m}]$ represents the distances between the vehicles and the RSU; $\mathbf{g}_m = [g_{1,m}, g_{2,m}, \dots, g_{k,m}]$ denotes the channel gains; $\mathbf{T}_m^{cm} = [T_{1,m}^{cm}, T_{2,m}^{cm}, \dots, T_{k,m}^{cm}]$ is the vehicles' communication latency for parameter uploads; and T_m represents the longest communication latency in the system.

2) *Action Space* \mathcal{A} : The actions involve determining an optimal strategy for vehicle selection, power allocation, quantization level, and bandwidth allocation index. At global round m , the agent's set of actions is

$$a_m = \{\mathbf{C}_m, \mathbf{Q}_m, \mathbf{B}_m\}. \quad (27)$$

This action triggers varying uploading times $T_{k,m}^{cm}$ with allocated bandwidth $b_{k,m}$ and quantization bits $q_{k,m}$ for selected vehicle satisfying $c_{k,m} = 1$. Then, T_m is updated according to (14) at global round m . During this period, vehicles traverse new distances at $u_{k,m}$, each corresponding to a distance $d_{k,m}$ from the RSU. The varying positions lead to different channel gains $g_{k,m}$, which subsequently impact the uploading time at the next round.

3) *Transition Probabilities* \mathcal{P} : The transition function $p(s_{m+1}|s_m, a_m)$ is the transition probability from the current state to the next state when the agent takes action a_m .

4) *Reward* \mathcal{R} : Our objective is to optimize the model performance by maximizing a reward. Designing the reward

has a pivotal impact on the training performance. The formulation of the reward function is based on the formulation in (24), which aims to maximize the number of accumulated participants and minimize the total latency. We include the two objectives in the reward function

$$r_{\text{obj}}(s_m, a_m) = \lambda_1 \bar{f}_1 - \lambda_2 \bar{f}_2. \quad (28)$$

To maximize the reward r_{obj} , reducing the quantization bit can decrease the transmitted model size, consequently reducing latency. However, a small quantization bit can enhance the quantization error, which is restricted within \mathcal{C}_1 to maintain the FL performance. Therefore, to ensure the quantization error constraint, we propose the following penalty:

$$r_c(s_m, a_m) = -\kappa \left| \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{c_{k,m} \rho_k \beta_{k,m}}{(2_{k,m}^q - 1)^2 \varepsilon} - 1 \right| \quad (29)$$

where κ is a dynamic hyperparameter to satisfy the constraint requirement and balance the objects and the constraint in the reward function. Then, the reward function can be calculated as the sum of the expected reward and penalty as

$$r_m = r_{\text{obj}}(s_m, a_m) + r_c(s_m, a_m). \quad (30)$$

Then, the cumulative discounted reward can be expressed as $R_m = \sum_{\epsilon=0}^{\infty} \gamma^\epsilon r_{m+\epsilon}$ with the discount factor γ .

C. DRL-Based Subproblem Solution

To address the optimization challenge involving both the discrete and continuous variables, we introduce a PPO-based framework [46]. PPO is a model-free, on-policy, and the policy gradient-based RL algorithm developed by OpenAI [47]. PPO achieves a balance between ease of implementation, sample efficiency, and tuning simplicity while enforcing minimal policy deviations via a clipping technique.

Let π_θ denote the policy determined by the parameter θ , and $\pi_\theta(a_m|s_m) = P(a_m|s_m, \theta)$ describes the probability to take action a_m given the state s_m . To solve the optimization problem, the agent interacts with the environment to seek the optimum policy π^* . The value network can be denoted as V_ψ determined by the parameter ψ . We denote \hat{A}_m as the advantage function

$$\hat{A}_m = r_m + \gamma V_\psi(s_{m+1}) - V_\psi(s_m). \quad (31)$$

The probability ratio of the current policy to the old policy is defined as $p_m(\theta) = [\pi_\theta(a_m|s_m)/\pi_{\theta'}(a_m|s_m)]$, where θ' is the parameter of the final step. To get the optimal policy while mitigating the excessively large policy deviation, the policy network maximizes a clipped surrogate objective function, as follows:

$$L_P(\theta) = \hat{\mathbb{E}}_m \left[\min \left(p_m(\theta) \hat{A}_m, \text{clip}(p_m(\theta), 1 - \nu, 1 + \nu) \hat{A}_m \right) \right] \quad (32)$$

where $\text{clip}(x, 1 - \nu, 1 + \nu) = \max(\min(x, 1 + \nu), 1 - \nu)$ with the hyper parameter ν limits the clipping range of x in $[1 - \nu, 1 + \nu]$. This clip function limits the magnitude of policy updates, enhancing the algorithm's stability and convergence.

Algorithm 2: PPO-Based Joint Vehicle Selection and Resource Allocation Algorithm

- 1: **Input:** The reward discount factor γ , the clipping parameter ν
 - 2: **Output:** The optimal model parameters θ^* , ψ^*
 - 3: Initialize policy network parameters θ , and value network parameters ψ .
 - 4: **for** $e = 1, 2, \dots$ **do**
 - 5: Apply policy π_θ in the environment and collect the set of trajectories.
 - 6: Compute the reward R_m .
 - 7: Compute the advantage function according to (31).
 - 8: Update the parameter θ of the policy network by maximizing (32) based on the parameters θ', θ .
 - 9: Update the parameter ψ of the value network by minimizing (33).
 - 10: Update the policy parameters $\theta' \leftarrow \theta$.
 - 11: **end for**
-

The value network aims to minimize the mean-squared error loss, as follows:

$$L_V(\psi) = \mathbb{E} \left[(V_\psi(s_m) - R_m)^2 \right]. \quad (33)$$

The proposed PPO-based method is outlined in Algorithm 2. It initializes the NN parameters θ, ψ and interacts with the environment to observe vehicle positions and latency during each episode. Actions are selected based on the policy, determining vehicle selection, resource allocation, and quantization level assignment. Through this interaction, the PPO collects samples, computes rewards, and then obtains the advantage function. Due to the clipping technique, the policy can be updated when the advantage function falls within a reasonable range, determined by the threshold ν .

Then, the complete procedure of the quantized FL in the vehicular networks can be found in Algorithm 3. The major complexity of Algorithm 3 lies in optimizing **C**, **Q**, and **B** in problem (24). To obtain the optimal results, the key complexity lies in executing Algorithm 1 with a loop of length T , where the outcome of $\omega_{\lambda'}^*$ in each iteration is determined by Algorithm 2. Obtaining $\omega_{\lambda'}^*$ in Algorithm 2 involves the PPO algorithm, with complexity $\mathcal{O}(|\theta| + |\psi|)$, where $|\theta|$ and $|\psi|$ denote the number of parameters in the policy and value function networks [48]. Hence, the total complexity of the proposed Algorithm 3 is $\mathcal{O}(T(|\theta| + |\psi|))$.

VI. SIMULATION RESULT

A. Simulation Settings

To demonstrate the effectiveness of our proposed algorithm, we conduct a series of simulations. We assume the RSU is deployed $H = 10$ m away from the road with a coverage radius of 500 m. There are $K = 10$ vehicles uniformly distributed between the entrance of the coverage and 100 m away from the entrance. From (9), we understand that the computation time depends on the system capacity when the bss are uniform across all vehicles, and we model the computation time for

Algorithm 3: Quantized FL in Vehicular Networks

- 1: The RSU initializes global model parameters \mathbf{w}_0 and sends global model to all vehicles.
- 2: The RSU determines the optimal selection indices \mathbf{C} , quantization bit assignment \mathbf{Q} and the bandwidth allocation \mathbf{B} by solving the MOP in (24) based on Algorithm 1.
- 3: **for** $m = 1$ to M **do**
- 4: **for** each selected client k in \mathcal{K} **do**
- 5: $\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^0 \leftarrow \mathbf{w}_0$.
- 6: **for** $i = 1$ to I **do**
- 7: $\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^i = \mathbf{w}_{k,m}^{i-1} - \eta_m \nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_{k,m}^{i-1}, \xi_{k,m}^{i-1})$ according to (2).
- 8: **end for**
- 9: Calculate $\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m} = \mathbf{w}_{k,m} - \mathbf{w}_{m-1}$ derived in (3).
- 10: Calculate $\Delta w_{k,m}^{\max}$ and $\Delta w_{k,m}^{\min}$ across all parameters in $\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}$.
- 11: **for** each parameter j in $\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}$ with a total J parameters **do**
- 12: Calculate the interval based on $q_{k,m}$.
- 13: Calculate the indices of parameter j in the interval.
- 14: A lower bound and an upper bound is given based on the indices.
- 15: Calculate the probability for the parameter to fall within the range of the two bounds

$$\iota_k = \frac{z_{\varphi+1} - |\Delta w_{k,m,j}|}{z_{\varphi+1} - z_{\varphi}}$$
- 16: Generate a random value $\Omega \in [0, 1]$.
- 17: **if** $\iota_k < \Omega$ **then**
- 18: The quantized value equals its lower bound.
- 19: **else**
- 20: The quantized value equals its upper bound.
- 21: **end if**
- 22: The sign of the quantized value is the same as the original parameter.
- 23: **end for**
- 24: Upload $Q(\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m})$ with $b_{k,m}B$ bandwidth to RSU.
- 25: **end for**
- 26: The RSU aggregates local model updates according to (5).
- 27: The RSU sends global model \mathbf{w}_m to all vehicles.
- 28: **end for**
- 29: **Return** the final global model \mathbf{w}_M

vehicles as an uniform process with a range of 10 ms for each local round. In addition, we consider there are $T = 11$ subproblems in the decomposition procedure. The remaining simulation parameters are outlined in Table I.

The goal of the FL task is to solve an image classification problem using the CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 data sets [49]. In both data sets, each vehicle is allocated the same amount of data, so they share equal weight ρ_k . We leverage Python 3.8 with Pytorch as the software platform. For the NN model, we apply the ResNet-20 [50], which consists of 19 convolutional layers and 1 fully connected layer, and the original size is

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameters	Values
Local epochs (I)	5
The maximum quantization bits (q^{max})	32 bits
Uplink transmission bandwidth (B)	20 MHz
Noise power (σ^2)	-104 dBm
Channel power gain at the reference distance of 1 m (h)	-34 dBm
Uplink power (p)	30 dBm
Path loss exponent (ν)	2
Episode (E)	20,000
Clip range (v)	0.2
Discount factor (γ)	0.99

Fig. 4. Value of the reward as the number of episodes varies for different algorithms.

1 MB. We utilize the Adam optimizer for optimization, and the local epochs are set to 5. For simplicity in analysis, we assume that the value of $\beta_{k,m}$ is similar across all vehicles like in [25].

Additionally, we also conduct the simulations on two benchmarks, which are as follows.

- 1) *Random Bandwidth Allocation (RBA)*: Each vehicle's bandwidth is randomly allocated, but other variables are optimized using the DRL-VQFL algorithm.
- 2) *Random Quantization Assignment (RQA)*: Quantization levels are randomly assigned, while other variables follow the DRL-VQFL algorithm.

B. Performance Evaluation and Analysis

Fig. 4 depicts the accumulated rewards with confidence bands for different methods as the episodes vary. It can be found that our proposed DRL-VQFL consistently outperforms the RBA and RQA methods due to the joint optimization of client selection, bandwidth allocation, and quantization levels, which increase vehicle participation while reducing latency. In RBA, inefficient bandwidth allocation can result in the straggler effect, extending the overall training time. In RQA, vehicles fail to strike a balance between the quantization error budget, the minimum latency requirement, and the number of participants. Some vehicles may employ a small quantization bit, which leads to fewer vehicles participating owing to the

Fig. 5. Value of the reward with different bss.

Fig. 6. Value of the reward under different lr.

quantization error constraint. Furthermore, we can see that by replacing the PPO framework with Advantage Actor-Critic (A2C), the A2C method yields lower rewards compared to PPO when solving (24). PPO’s advantage over A2C can be attributed to its utilization of the clipped surrogate objective function, which effectively limits policy update magnitudes, thus enhancing algorithmic stability and convergence.

Fig. 5 illustrates the performance of the three methods under varying bss. It can be seen that all curves exhibit convergence except for the curve corresponding to RQA with a bs of 128. This deviation is attributed to RQA’s utilization of a random quantization allocation policy, where the quantization error constraint may be violated even in the final stages of training, resulting in a substantial penalty. We can find that the RBA method yields similar rewards across various bss, which are lower compared to those achieved by DRL-VQFL. This is because the random allocation of bandwidth in RBA leads to an inefficient system with longer latency. Moreover, regardless of the chosen bs, DRL-VQFL consistently outperforms the other two baselines in terms of the reward. We observe that the DRL-VQFL achieves the highest reward when utilizing a bs of 64, so we set the bs as 64 for subsequent simulations.

Fig. 6 shows the convergence performance with different learning rates (lrs). In this figure, we can observe that the

Fig. 7. Reward versus latency tolerance for different algorithms.

DRL-VQFL outperforms the RBA and RQA methods across all lr. Specifically, all three methods can obtain the largest reward when lr is set to 0.01. Furthermore, it can be seen that the DRL-VQFL becomes convergent at approximately 5000 episodes when both the policy network and the value network have an lr of 0.01. As the lr decreases to 0.001, DRL-VQFL converges to a lower reward value at around 7500 episodes. Moreover, a further decrease in the lr to 0.0001 results in a decreased convergence rate, stabilizing at a lower reward value of around 10000 episodes. Hence, to demonstrate the efficiency of DRL-VQFL, we set the lr to 0.01 in the following simulations.

Fig. 7 depicts the reward as functions of the latency tolerance T^{\max} at one global round. DRL-VQFL outperforms the other two baselines across all the T^{\max} values, highlighting its overall superiority. In DRL-VQFL, the reward first increases with larger T^{\max} , because larger T^{\max} allows less bandwidth for uploading, so more vehicles can participate. Then, the reward stabilizes approximately when $T^{\max} > 0.6$ s, as enough vehicles can engage, and the number of participants and latency remain consistent. In RBA, the reward initially benefits from the optimal quantization bit allocation but subsequently decreases as the vehicles fail to acquire sufficient bandwidth to complete the tasks within the allowed latency. In RQA, the reward remains at a low value, because incorrect quantization allocation triggers the quantization error penalty, causing the agent to prioritize constraint adherence over reward maximization. Additionally, a sharp decline is observed in RQA when $T^{\max} = 0.35$ s, which can be attributed to fewer vehicles participating in FL training, making it easier to meet the quantization error constraint.

Fig. 8 plots the accumulated number of selected vehicles for different algorithms under various quantization error constraints. In DRL-VQFL (loose), RBA, and RQA, the same quantization error constraint is applied, while a smaller quantization error constraint is utilized in DRL-VQFL (tight). We can find that the accumulated number of selected vehicles in all curves increases as the latency tolerance T^{\max} becomes larger. This is because a larger T^{\max} allows more vehicles to utilize the allocated bandwidth to upload their parameters

Fig. 8. Accumulated number of selected vehicles for different algorithms under various quantization error constraints.

Fig. 9. Time delay for different latency tolerance versus the FL iteration numbers.

within the allowed latency. We can also observe that the value in DRL-VQFL (loose) exceeds those in RBA and RQA. This difference arises because RBA can lead to the straggler effect, reducing the actual number of participants, while random quantization allocation can result in a larger quantization error, leading to fewer vehicles being selected. We also notice that the DRL-VQFL (tight) archives lower values compared to the DRL-VQFL (loose) when T^{\max} is small because the quantization error constraint limits the number of selected vehicles to satisfy the desired latency requirement. However, as T^{\max} becomes larger, DRL-VQFL (tight) and DRL-VQFL (loose) can obtain similar values.

Fig. 9 displays the latency under various latency tolerance T^{\max} constraints. We can find that as T^{\max} increases, the latency in each FL iteration also increases, and the difference of each curve diminishes. Besides, it can be observed that the latency for $T^{\max} = 0.3$ and $T^{\max} = 0.35$ keep decreasing, indicating that the latency decreases at each round as vehicles approach the RSU with improved wireless channel conditions. When $T^{\max} \geq 0.4$, the curves of latency exhibit convexity. This is because as the latency tolerance increases, the vehicles travel a longer distance, resulting in initially decreasing and then increasing distances between the vehicles and the RSU.

Fig. 10(c) shows the training loss and the testing accuracy of the CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 data sets as the latency increases in seconds. We compare the FL performance under the four different quantization error constraints $\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3$, and ε_4 ($\varepsilon_1 < \varepsilon_2 < \varepsilon_3 < \varepsilon_4$) with the lossless scheme (MaxBits), where all the vehicles upload the local models with the maximum quantization bit q^{\max} . It can be found that a tighter quantization error constraint achieves lower loss and higher testing accuracy, with the tightest constraint approximating the performance of the lossless scheme. In addition, as the quantization error constraint becomes looser, the convergence rate accelerates. This is because a looser constraint allows for smaller quantization bits, resulting in a smaller size of the transmitted model.

In Fig. 11(c), the training losses and testing accuracy under different optimization algorithms for the CIFAR-10 and the CIFAR-100 data sets are depicted. Across all the subfigures, it can be observed that the DRL-VQFL achieves comparable loss and accuracy to RBA with significantly reduced latency, underscoring the superiority of DRL-VQFL in terms of convergence rate. This is because the efficient bandwidth allocation in DRL-VQFL avoids the occurrence of the straggler effect and minimizes unexpected latency. Moreover, even though DRL-VQFL demonstrates a slightly longer latency compared to RQA in both the data sets, it consistently and significantly outperforms RQA at equivalent latency levels in terms of both training loss and testing accuracy. This can be attributed to optimized quantization allocation in DRL-VQFL, which facilitates greater participant involvement while satisfying the quantization error constraint and reducing the total latency.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this article, we have investigated the performance and efficiency of FL within vehicle networks by incorporating the quantization scheme into the local models before uplink transmission. Through a theoretical derivation of the convergence rate of the convex loss function in FL, we have gained insights into how the quantization error and the number of participating clients impact the FL performance. Following that, we have formulated an MOP intending to maximize the participation of clients while minimizing the overall latency via the joint design of quantization levels, bandwidth allocation, and client selection. To tackle this MOP, we have employed the decomposition strategy to break down the original problem into several scalar subproblems. We also leveraged the parameter transfer strategy to establish the initial parameters for each subproblem. For each subproblem, we have converted it to an MDP, considering vehicles' high mobility and dynamic wireless channel conditions. Then, we proposed the DRL-VQFL approach to solve the MDP. Through extensive numerical results and simulations, our proposed scheme has consistently demonstrated superior performance and efficiency in terms of learning accuracy and total training latency. Therefore, DRL-VQFL effectively harnesses the potential of vehicular networks while addressing the challenges posed by the quantization errors and dynamic conditions. In the future, we will investigate split learning (SL), which divides the deep models into

Fig. 10. Training loss and the testing accuracy of the CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 data sets with the ResNet20 model. (a) Training loss on CIFAR-10. (b) Testing accuracy on CIFAR-10. (c) Training loss on CIFAR-100. (d) Testing accuracy on CIFAR-100.

submodels trained separately on the vehicles to protect the clients' privacy and improve the learning performance in the non-iid data setting. We will explore integrating SL into the FL-enabled vehicular networks, taking into account the high mobility of vehicles to pave the way for ITSs in vehicular networks.

APPENDIX

From the L-smoothness in Assumption 1, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}_m)] - F(\mathbf{w}^*) \\
 & \leq \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[\langle \nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}^*), (\mathbf{w}_m - \mathbf{w}^*) \rangle]}_{A_1} + \frac{L}{2} \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{w}_m - \mathbf{w}^*\|_2^2]}_{A_2} \\
 & \stackrel{(a)}{\leq} \frac{L}{2} \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{w}_m - \mathbf{w}^*\|_2^2]}_{A_2} \quad (34)
 \end{aligned}$$

where the inequality (a) is because $\nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}^*) = 0$, leads to $A_1 = 0$. To expand A_2 , we introduce an auxiliary variable $\mathbf{v}_m = \mathbf{w}_{m-1} + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_m} \rho_k \Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}$.

Then, we define $\Delta_m = A_2$, which can be transformed as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta_m & = \mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{w}_m - \mathbf{v}_m + \mathbf{v}_m - \mathbf{w}^*\|_2^2] \\
 & = \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{w}_m - \mathbf{v}_m\|_2^2]}_{B_1} + \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{v}_m - \mathbf{w}^*\|_2^2]}_{B_2} \\
 & \quad + 2 \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[\langle \mathbf{w}_m - \mathbf{v}_m, \mathbf{v}_m - \mathbf{w}^* \rangle]}_{B_3} \\
 & \stackrel{(a)}{=} \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{w}_m - \mathbf{v}_m\|_2^2]}_{B_1} + \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[\|\mathbf{v}_m - \mathbf{w}^*\|_2^2]}_{B_2} \quad (35)
 \end{aligned}$$

where the equality (a) arises from $\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{w}_m - \mathbf{v}_m] = 0$ due to the first equation in Lemma 1, consequently leading to $B_3 = 0$.

Following that, B_1 can be converted as

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_1 & \stackrel{(a)}{=} \mathbb{E} \left[\left\| \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_m} \rho_k (Q(\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}) - \Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}) \right\|_2^2 \right] \\
 & \stackrel{(b)}{\leq} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_m} \rho_k \mathbb{E} \left[\|(Q(\Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}) - \Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m})\|_2^2 \right] \\
 & \stackrel{(c)}{\leq} \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_m} \rho_k O_{k,m} \quad (36)
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 11. FL performance in the CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 data sets for different algorithms. (a) Training loss on the CIFAR-10 data set. (b) Testing accuracy on the CIFAR-10 data set. (c) Training loss on the CIFAR-100 data set. (d) Testing accuracy on the CIFAR-100 data set.

where the equality (a) is due to the definition of \mathbf{w}_m and \mathbf{v}_m . Inequality (b) is by the Jensen's inequality, and the inequality (c) is due to the second equation in Lemma 1.

We define another auxiliary variable as $\mathbf{u}_m = \mathbf{w}_{m-1} + \sum_{k=1}^K \rho_k \Delta \mathbf{w}_{k,m}$. Therefore, B_2 can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
 B_2 &= \mathbb{E} \left[\|\mathbf{v}_m - \mathbf{u}_m + \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{w}^*\|_2^2 \right] \\
 &= \mathbb{E} \left[\|\mathbf{v}_m - \mathbf{u}_m\|_2^2 \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\|\mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{w}^*\|_2^2 \right] \\
 &\quad + 2\mathbb{E} \left[\langle \mathbf{v}_m - \mathbf{u}_m, \mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{w}^* \rangle \right] \\
 &\stackrel{(a)}{=} \mathbb{E} \left[\|\mathbf{v}_m - \mathbf{u}_m\|_2^2 \right] + \mathbb{E} \left[\|\mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{w}^*\|_2^2 \right] \\
 &\stackrel{(b)}{\leq} \eta_{m-1}^2 W_1 + \underbrace{\mathbb{E} \left[\|\mathbf{u}_m - \mathbf{w}^*\|_2^2 \right]}_{C_1} \quad (37)
 \end{aligned}$$

where the equality (a) is due to the random selection leading to $\mathbf{v}_m = \mathbf{u}_m$, and the inequality (b) is obtained from Lemma 5 in [37] regarding the bounding variance of \mathbf{v}_m with $W_1 = [4I^2G^2/K - 1](K/N - 1)$.

When η_m varies across all global round $m \in \mathcal{M}$, C_1 can be bounded from [27, Lemma 3]

$$C_1 \leq (1 - \eta_{m-1}\mu)\Delta_{m-1} + (\eta_{m-1})^2W_2 \quad (38)$$

where $W_2 = I^2\delta^2 + 2LI^2\Gamma + [G^2(I-1)(2I-1)(\mu+2)/6] + IG^2$.

Let $\eta_m = (\chi/\tau + m)$ with $\chi \geq (1/\mu)$ and $\tau \geq \chi$. Assume the inequality $\Delta_m \leq (v/\tau + m) + U_m$ holds for $m \in \mathcal{M}$, where $U_m = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_i} \rho_k O_{k,i}$ and $v \leq \max\{\chi^2(W_1 + W_2)/\chi\mu - 1, \tau\Delta_0\}$. With the above derivations, we use the induction method also applied in [37] to prove our assumption

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta_{m+1} &\leq (1 - \eta_m\mu)\Delta_m + \eta_m^2(W_1 + W_2) + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_{m+1}} \rho_k O_{k,m+1} \\
 &\leq \left(1 - \frac{\chi\mu}{\tau + m}\right) \left(\frac{v}{\tau + m} + U_m\right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{\chi^2(W_1 + W_2)}{(\tau + m)^2} + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_{m+1}} \rho_k O_{k,m+1} \\
 &= \frac{\tau + m - 1}{(\tau + m)^2} v + \left(\frac{\chi^2(W_1 + W_2)}{(\tau + m)^2} - \frac{\chi\mu - 1}{(\tau + m)^2} v\right) \\
 &\quad + \frac{\tau + m - \chi\mu}{\tau + m} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_i} \rho_k O_{k,i} + \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_{m+1}} \rho_k O_{k,m+1} \\
 &\leq \frac{v}{\tau + m + 1} + U_{m+1}. \quad (39)
 \end{aligned}$$

Let $\chi = (2/\mu)$, and then from the definition of ν we have

$$\begin{aligned} \nu &\leq \max \left\{ \frac{\chi^2(W_1 + W_2)}{\chi\mu - 1}, \tau\Delta_0 \right\} \\ &\leq \frac{\chi^2(W_1 + W_2)}{\chi\mu - 1} + \tau\Delta_0 \\ &\leq \frac{4(W_1 + W_2)}{\mu^2} + \tau\Delta_0. \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

Then, $\mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}_m)] - F(\mathbf{w}^*)$ can be bounded as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}[F(\mathbf{w}_m)] - F(\mathbf{w}^*) &\leq \frac{L}{2} \left(\frac{\nu}{\tau + m} + U_m \right) \\ &\leq \frac{L}{(\tau + m)} \left(\frac{\tau}{2} \Delta_0 + \frac{2(W_1 + W_2)}{\mu^2} \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{L}{2} \left(\sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{k \in \mathcal{N}_i} \frac{\rho_k \beta_{k,i}}{(2^{q_{k,i}} - 1)^2} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Therefore, the proof of Theorem 1 is completed.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Alam, J. Ferreira and J. Fonseca, "Introduction to intelligent transportation systems," in *Intelligent Transportation Systems: Dependable Vehicular Communications for Improved Road Safety*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2016, pp. 1–17.
- [2] S. Chen, J. Hu, Y. Shi, and L. Zhao, "LTE-V: A TD-LTE-based V2X solution for future vehicular network," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 997–1005, Dec. 2016.
- [3] M. N. Mejri, J. Ben-Othman, and M. Hamdi, "Survey on VANET security challenges and possible cryptographic solutions," *Veh. Commun.*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 53–66, Apr. 2014.
- [4] Z. Lu, G. Qu, and Z. Liu, "A survey on recent advances in vehicular network security, trust, and privacy," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 760–776, Feb. 2019.
- [5] H. Ye, L. Liang, G. Ye Li, J. Kim, L. Lu, and M. Wu, "Machine learning for vehicular networks: Recent advances and application examples," *IEEE Veh. Technol. Mag.*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 94–101, Jun. 2018.
- [6] F. Tang, Y. Kawamoto, N. Kato, and J. Liu, "Future intelligent and secure vehicular network toward 6G: Machine-learning approaches," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 108, no. 2, pp. 292–307, Feb. 2020.
- [7] B. McMahan, E. Moore, D. Ramage, S. Hampson, and B. A. Y. Arcas, "Communication-efficient learning of deep networks from decentralized data," in *Proc. Int. Conf. AI Statist.*, 2017, pp. 1273–1282.
- [8] D. C. Nguyen, M. Ding, P. N. Pathirana, A. Seneviratne, J. Li, and H. V. Poor, "Federated learning for Internet of Things: A comprehensive survey," *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 1622–1658, 3rd Quart., 2021.
- [9] S. Raza, S. Wang, M. Ahmed, and M. R. Anwar, "A survey on vehicular edge computing: Architecture, applications, technical issues, and future directions," *Wireless Commun. Mobile Comput.*, vol. 2019, Feb. 2019, Art. no. e3159762.
- [10] F. Tang, B. Mao, N. Kato, and G. Gui, "Comprehensive survey on machine learning in vehicular network: Technology, applications and challenges," *IEEE Commun. Surveys Tuts.*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 2027–2057, 3rd Quart., 2021.
- [11] X. Zhang, J. Liu, T. Hu, Z. Chang, Y. Zhang, and G. Min, "Federated learning-assisted vehicular edge computing: Architecture and research directions," *IEEE Veh. Technol. Mag.*, vol. 18, no. 4, pp. 75–84, Dec. 2023.
- [12] Z. Zhao, J. Xia, L. Fan, X. Lei, G. K. Karagiannidis, and A. Nallanathan, "System optimization of federated learning networks with a constrained latency," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 71, no. 1, pp. 1095–1100, Jan. 2022.
- [13] K. Yang, T. Jiang, Y. Shi, and Z. Ding, "Federated learning via over-the-air computation," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 2022–2035, Mar. 2020.
- [14] J. Zhu, Y. Shi, Y. Zhou, C. Jiang, W. Chen, and K. B. Letaief, "Over-the-air federated learning and optimization," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 11, no. 10, pp. 16996–17020, May 2024.
- [15] T. Zeng, O. Semriari, M. Chen, W. Saad, and M. Bennis, "Federated learning on the road autonomous controller design for connected and autonomous vehicles," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 21, no. 12, pp. 10407–10423, Dec. 2022.
- [16] H. Xiao, J. Zhao, Q. Pei, J. Feng, L. Liu, and W. Shi, "Vehicle selection and resource optimization for federated learning in vehicular edge computing," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 23, no. 8, pp. 11073–11087, Aug. 2022.
- [17] S. Zheng, C. Shen, and X. Chen, "Design and analysis of uplink and downlink communications for federated learning," *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, vol. 39, no. 7, pp. 2150–2167, Jul. 2021.
- [18] M. Kim, W. Saad, M. Mozaffari, and M. Debbah, "Green, quantized federated learning over wireless networks: An energy-efficient design," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 1386–1402, Feb. 2024.
- [19] R. Chen, D. Shi, X. Qin, D. Liu, M. Pan, and S. Cui, "Service delay minimization for federated learning over mobile devices," *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, vol. 41, no. 4, pp. 990–1006, Apr. 2023.
- [20] S. Wang, M. Chen, C. G. Brinton, C. Yin, W. Saad, and S. Cui, "Performance optimization for variable bandwidth federated learning in wireless networks," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 2340–2356, Mar. 2024.
- [21] A. Reisizadeh, A. Mokhtari, H. Hassani, A. Jadbabaie, and R. Pedarsani, "FedPAQ: A communication-efficient federated learning method with periodic averaging and quantization," in *Proc. Int. Conf. AI Statist.*, 2020, pp. 2021–2031.
- [22] N. Yang et al., "Model-based reinforcement learning for quantized federated learning performance optimization," in *Proc. IEEE Glob. Commun. Conf.*, 2022, pp. 5063–5068.
- [23] P. Prakash et al., "IoT device friendly and communication-efficient federated learning via joint model pruning and quantization," *IEEE Internet Things J.*, vol. 9, no. 15, pp. 13638–13650, Aug. 2022.
- [24] S. Chen, C. Shen, L. Zhang, and Y. Tang, "Dynamic aggregation for heterogeneous quantization in federated learning," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 20, no. 10, pp. 6804–6819, Oct. 2021.
- [25] Y. Wang, Y. Xu, Q. Shi, and T.-H. Chang, "Quantized federated learning under transmission delay and outage constraints," *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 323–341, Jan. 2022.
- [26] K. Ozkara, N. Singh, D. Data, and S. Diggavi, "QuPeD: Quantized personalization via distillation with applications to federated learning," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 34, 2021, pp. 3622–3634.
- [27] P. S. Bouzinis, P. D. Diamantoulakis, and G. K. Karagiannidis, "Wireless quantized federated learning: A joint computation and communication design," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 71, no. 5, pp. 2756–2770, May 2023.
- [28] M. Lan, Q. Ling, S. Xiao, and W. Zhang, "Quantization bits allocation for wireless federated learning," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 22, no. 11, pp. 8336–8351, Nov. 2023.
- [29] Y. Li, Y. Guo, M. Alazab, S. Chen, C. Shen, and K. Yu, "Joint optimal quantization and aggregation of federated learning scheme in VANETs," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 23, no. 10, pp. 19852–19863, Oct. 2022.
- [30] S. Gupta, A. Agrawal, K. Gopalakrishnan, and P. Narayanan, "Deep learning with limited numerical precision," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Mach. Learn.*, 2015, pp. 1–10.
- [31] J. Posner, L. Tseng, M. Aloqaily, and Y. Jararweh, "Federated learning in vehicular networks: Opportunities and solutions," *IEEE Netw.*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 152–159, Mar./Apr. 2021.
- [32] J. Ren, G. Yu, and G. Ding, "Accelerating DNN training in wireless federated edge learning systems," *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 219–232, Jan. 2021.
- [33] X. Zhang, Z. Chang, G. Zhang, M. Li, and Y. Hu, "Trajectory optimization and resource allocation for time minimization in the UAV-enabled MEC system," in *Proc. IEEE Wireless Commun. Netw. Conf.*, Austin, TX, USA, 2022, pp. 333–338.
- [34] J. Xu and H. Wang, "Client selection and bandwidth allocation in wireless federated learning networks: A long-term perspective," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 1188–1200, Feb. 2021.
- [35] S. Liu, G. Yu, R. Yin, J. Yuan, L. Shen, and C. Liu, "Joint model pruning and device selection for communication-efficient federated edge learning," *IEEE Trans. Commun.*, vol. 70, no. 1, pp. 231–244, Jan. 2022.
- [36] Z. Yang, M. Chen, W. Saad, C. S. Hong, and M. Shikh-Bahaei, "Energy efficient federated learning over wireless communication networks," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 20, no. 3, pp. 1935–1949, Mar. 2021.
- [37] X. Li, K. Huang, W. Yang, S. Wang, and Z. Zhang, "On the convergence of FedAVG on non-IID data," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Learn. Represent.*, 2020, pp. 1–26.
- [38] C. Li, C. Li, Y. Zhao, B. Zhang, and C. Li, "An efficient multi-model training algorithm for federated learning," in *Proc. IEEE Glob. Commun. Conf.*, Madrid, Spain, 2021, pp. 1–6.
- [39] K. Li, T. Zhang, and R. Wang, "Deep reinforcement learning for multiobjective optimization," *IEEE Trans. Cybern.*, vol. 51, no. 6, pp. 3103–3114, Jun. 2021.

- [40] X. Xu et al., "A computation offloading method over big data for IoT-enabled cloud-edge computing," *Future Gener. Comput. Syst.*, vol. 95, pp. 522–533, Jun. 2019.
- [41] H. Huang, K. Peng, and X. Xu, "Collaborative computation offloading for smart cities in mobile edge computing," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Cloud Comput.*, Beijing, China, 2020, pp. 176–183.
- [42] K. Miettinen, *Nonlinear Multiobjective Optimization*, vol. 12. New York, NY, USA: Springer, 1999.
- [43] Q. Zhang and H. Li, "MOEA/D: A multiobjective evolutionary algorithm based on decomposition," *IEEE Trans. Evol. Comput.*, vol. 11, no. 6, pp. 712–731, Dec. 2007.
- [44] X. Tu and K. Zhu, "Learning-based multi-objective resource allocation for over-the-air federated learning," in *Proc. IEEE Glob. Commun. Conf.*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 2022, pp. 3065–3070.
- [45] Y. Xu, K. Zhu, H. Xu, and J. Ji, "Deep reinforcement learning for multi-objective resource allocation in multi-platoon cooperative vehicular networks," *IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun.*, vol. 22, no. 9, pp. 6185–6198, Sep. 2023.
- [46] J. Schulman, F. Wolski, P. Dhariwal, A. Radford, and O. Klimov, "Proximal policy optimization algorithms," 2017, [arXiv:1707.06347](https://arxiv.org/abs/1707.06347).
- [47] A. Al-Hilo, M. Samir, C. Assi, S. Sharafeddine, and D. Ebrahimi, "UAV-assisted content delivery in intelligent transportation systems-joint trajectory planning and cache management," *IEEE Trans. Intell. Transp. Syst.*, vol. 22, no. 8, pp. 5155–5167, Aug. 2021.
- [48] R. Zhang, K. Xiong, Y. Lu, P. Fan, D. W. K. Ng, and K. B. Letaief, "Energy efficiency maximization in RIS-assisted SWIPT networks with RSMA: A PPO-based approach," *IEEE J. Sel. Areas Commun.*, vol. 41, no. 5, pp. 1413–1430, May 2023.
- [49] A. Krizhevsky and G. Hinton, "Learning multiple layers of features from tiny images," M.S. thesis, Dept. Comput. Sci., Univ. Toronto, Toronto, ON, Canada, 2009. [Online]. Available: <http://www.cs.toronto.edu/~kriz/learning-features-2009-TR.pdf>
- [50] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, "Deep residual learning for image recognition," in *Proc. IEEE Conf. Comput. Vis. Pattern Recognit.*, Las Vegas, NV, USA, 2016, pp. 770–778.

Xinran Zhang (Graduate Student Member, IEEE) received the B.S. degree in information and communication engineering from the University of Electronic Science and Technology of China (UESTC), Chengdu, China, in 2018, and the M.S. degree in electrical and computer engineering from Ohio State University, Columbus, OH, USA, in 2019. She is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree with the School of Computer Science and Engineering, UESTC.

She is also a visiting student with the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, University of Houston, Houston, TX, USA. Her research interests include federated learning, vehicular network, mobile computing, and machine learning.

Weilong Chen received the B.S. degree in electronic engineering from the University of Electronic Science and Technology of China, Chengdu, China, where he is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree.

He has published papers in top conferences, such as ACM MM and PAKDD. His research interests include machine learning, federated learning, and smart grid.

Hui Zhao (Graduate Student Member, IEEE) received the M.S. degree from the School of Computer Science, Beijing University of Technology, Beijing, China, in 2022. He is currently pursuing the Ph.D. degree with the School of Computer Science and Engineering, University of Electronic Science and Technology of China, Chengdu, China.

His research interests include UAV wireless networks, Internet of Things, and deep reinforcement learning.

Zheng Chang (Senior Member, IEEE) received the B.Eng. degree from Jilin University, Changchun, China, in 2007, the M.Sc. (Tech.) degree from Helsinki University of Technology (currently Aalto University), Espoo, Finland, in 2009, and the Ph.D. degree from the University of Jyväskylä, Jyväskylä, Finland, in 2013.

Since 2008, he has held various research positions with Helsinki University of Technology, University of Jyväskylä, and Magister Solutions Ltd., Jyväskylä. He was a Visiting Researcher with Tsinghua University, Beijing, China, from June to August in 2013, and the University of Houston, TX, USA, from April to May in 2015. He has published over 190 papers in journals and conferences. His research interests include IoT, cloud/edge computing, security and privacy, vehicular networks, and green communications.

Dr. Chang has been awarded as the 2018 IEEE Communications Society Best Young Researcher for Europe, Middle East, and Africa Region and the 2021 IEEE Communications Society MMTTC Outstanding Young Researcher. He received Best Paper Awards from IEEE ICC in 2023, IEEE TCGCC, and APCC in 2017. He has been awarded by the Ulla Tuominen Foundation, the Nokia Foundation, and the Riitta and Jorma J. Takanen Foundation for his research excellence. He serves as an Editor for IEEE WIRELESS COMMUNICATIONS LETTERS, *Wireless Networks and China Communications* (Springer), and a Guest Editor for IEEE NETWORK, IEEE WIRELESS COMMUNICATIONS, *IEEE Communications Magazine*, IEEE INTERNET OF THINGS JOURNAL, IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON INDUSTRIAL INFORMATICS, *Physical Communications*, *Journal on Wireless Communications and Networking* (EURASIP), and *Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing*. He also serves as the Symposium Co-Chair for IEEE ICC'20 and Globecom'23, the Publicity Co-Chair for IEEE Infocom'22, the Workshop Co-Chair for ICC'22, the TPC Co-Chair for IEEE iThing'22, and the TPC Member for many IEEE major conferences, such as INFOCOM, ICC, and Globecom. He was the exemplary reviewer of IEEE Wireless Communication Letters in 2018. He has participated in organizing workshop and special session in Globecom'19, WCNC'18-'24, SPAWC'19, and ISWCS'18.

Zhu Han (Fellow, IEEE) received the B.S. degree in electronic engineering from Tsinghua University, Beijing, China, in 1997, and the M.S. and Ph.D. degrees in electrical and computer engineering from the University of Maryland, College Park, MD, USA, in 1999 and 2003, respectively.

From 2000 to 2002, he was a Research and Development Engineer of JDSU, Germantown, MD. From 2003 to 2006, he was a Research Associate with the University of Maryland. From 2006 to 2008, he was an Assistant Professor with Boise State University, Boise, ID, USA. He is currently a John and Rebecca Moores Professor with the Electrical and Computer Engineering Department as well as with the Computer Science Department, University of Houston, Texas, TX, USA. His main research targets on the novel game-theory related concepts critical to enabling efficient and distributive use of wireless networks with limited resources. His other research interests include wireless resource allocation and management, wireless communications and networking, quantum computing, data science, smart grid, carbon neutralization, and security and privacy.

Dr. Han received an NSF Career Award in 2010, the Fred W. Ellersick Prize of the IEEE Communication Society in 2011, the EURASIP Best Paper Award for the Journal on Advances in Signal Processing in 2015, the IEEE Leonard G. Abraham Prize in the field of Communications Systems, the Best Paper Award in IEEE JSAC in 2016, IEEE Vehicular Technology Society 2022 Best Land Transportation Paper Award, and several best paper awards in IEEE conferences. He is also the winner of the 2021 IEEE Kiyo Tomiyasu Award (an IEEE Field Award), for outstanding early to mid-career contributions to technologies holding the promise of innovative applications, with the following citation: "For Contributions to Game Theory and Distributed Management of Autonomous Communication Networks." He has been an 1% Highly Cited Researcher since 2017 according to the Web of Science. He was an IEEE Communications Society Distinguished Lecturer from 2015 to 2018 and ACM Distinguished Speaker from 2022 to 2025, an AAAS fellow since 2019, and ACM Fellow since 2024.